

The Effectiveness of Salicylic Acid on Antibiotic Resistance, Biofilm Formation, and Activity of Efflux Pumps among *Acinetobacter Baumannii* Clinical Isolates

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Abstract

Objective: Salicylic acid (SA) has played a critical role in medicine throughout history and has an ever evolving and important role still today. Exposure of bacteria to SA effect cross-resistance to antimicrobial compounds, decreasing their ability to form biofilms and increasing persister cell populations. This research aim to evaluate the effect of SA on antibiotic resistance, biofilm formation and presence of efflux pump system of *Acinetobacter baumannii*.

Methods: A total of 35 *A. baumannii* isolates have been isolated from different clinical specimens and identified by vitek 2 compact system. Antibiotic resistance pattern toward 21 antibiotics, biofilm formation and efflux pump system were determine phenotypically using Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method, Congo red agar test, and Cart wheel method respectively. Phenotypic effect of 4mM of SA on antibiotic resistance pattern, biofilm formation and efflux pump system has been studied.

Results: All isolates (100%) showed resistance to ampicillin , cefepime , ceftazidime , ceftriaxone , cefotaxime , cefoxitin , aztreonam while The percentage of resistance to other studied antibiotics was range between 94.28% -34.28%. Strong biofilm producer isolates formed 17.14% while 2.80% and 80% of isolates showed weak and non- biofilm forming respectively. All isolates have the ability to producing efflux pumps. Using of SA cause decrease in antibiotic resistance of *A. baumannii* to some β lactam such as imipenem and aminoglycoside. Also it cause decrease in the ability of isolate to form biofilm and decrease in activity of efflux pump. SA play role in decreasing antibiotic resistance and virulence factors of *A. baumannii* suggestion possibility to use it in combination with antibiotics as drug of choice for treated of infection caused by *A. baumannii*.

Conclusion: SA play role in decreasing antibiotic resistance and virulence factors of *A. baumannii* suggestion possibility to use it in combination with antibiotics as drug of choice for treated of infection caused by *A. baumannii*.

Key words: *A. baumannii*, Salicylic acid, Antibiotic resistance, Biofilm formation, Efflux pump

1. INTRODUCTION

Acinetobacter baumannii is Gram-negative coccobacilli, strictly aerobic, oxidase-negative, non-lactose fermenting, opportunistic extracellular pathogen that is commonly referred to as a nosocomial infection [1]. It is associated with bloodstream infections in intensive care units, patients with central venous catheters, mechanical ventilation, pneumonia, respiratory and cardiovascular failure. Various clinical specimens from hospitalized patients have yielded the isolation of *A. baumannii* [2].

A. baumannii is one of the most prevalent and dangerous multiple drug resistance species that has been categorized under the “ESKAPE group” include *Enterococcus faecium*, *S. aureus*, *K. pneumoniae*, *A. baumannii*, *P. aeruginosa* and *Enterobacter* spp [3]. It is very worrying that *A. baumannii* are becoming resistant to almost all known antibiotics due to many mechanisms of antibiotics resistance such as enzymatic degradation of antibiotics, target site modification, altered membrane permeability, biofilm formation and multidrug efflux pumps [4]. Biofilm formation is an important virulence mechanism for bacteria where the maintenance and development of *A. baumannii* biofilms are influenced by different microbial characteristics such as adhesion, surface appendages, virulence genes, and resistance determinants, along with physicochemical factors like temperature, growth media, pH, and oxygen concentration [5]. Efflux pumps is the most bacterial resistance mechanism thought to be the primary driver of *A. baumannii* antibiotic resistance that developed from nosocomial due to the low absorbency of the outer membrane, and they have been crucial in drug resistance [6].

Treatment of bacterial infections with antimicrobials once revolutionized practices in medicine. Salicylic acid (SA) is a phytohormone and an active secondary metabolite occurring in plants and microorganisms, such as bacteria and fungi. SA and its derivatives (collectively called salicylates) are synthesized from chorismate (derived from shikimate pathway) [7]. Salicylic acids have been used in human and veterinary medicine for their anti-pyretic, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic properties for centuries. Many studies have established that SA is a key signal molecule in regulating the activation of local and systemic defense responses against infections by pathogens by affecting virulence in many opportunistic pathogens by decreasing their ability to form biofilms and increasing persister cell populations [8,9,10]. Due to a vital role of SA in pathogenicity of bacterial species and their biosynthesis of enzyme that serves as a prime target for inhibitory drug development, this research aimed to investigate the impact of salicylic acid on antibiotic-resistant, biofilm formation and the efflux pumps of *A. baumannii* isolates.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Bacterial Isolates

A total of 35 *A. baumannii* isolates were collected from various clinical specimens (sputum, urine, blood cultures, wounds, and burns) and identified according to their morphological characters, their ability to grow at 40°C and finally by Vitek 2 compact system using GN ID card.

2.2. Antibiotics Disk

Twenty one type of antibiotics including: ampicillin, amoxiclave, cefoxitin, colistin, chloramphenicol (Titan Biotech Ltd -India), cefepime, ceftazidime, ceftriaxone, cefotaxime, imipenem, meropenem, amikacin, gentamicin, tobramycin, netilmicin, ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, doxycycline, trimethoprim, chlindamycin (Biolab-Germany), and aztreonam (Bioanalyse- Turkey) have been used to determine the antibiotic resistance of *A. baumannii*.

2.3. Muller Hinton Agar

MHA plates free from SA and MHA plates supplemented with 4mM of SA have been used for detection of the pattern of antibiotics resistance and the effect on SA on antibiotics resistance pattern of *A. baumannii* respectively.

2.4. Congo Red Agar

Brain-Heart Infusion (BHI) broth supplemented with 0.08% of Congo red and 2% sucrose has been used for detection of biofilm formation, as well as BHI broth supplemented with 0.08% of Congo red, 2% sucrose and 4mM of SA has been used for detection the effect of SA on biofilm formation.

2.5. Tryptic Soy Agar

TSA plates supplemented with different concentration of Ethidium Bromide (0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2, µg/ml) as well as TSA plates supplemented with 4mM of SA and different concentration of Ethidium Bromide (0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2, µg/ml) have been used for detection of efflux pump and the effect on SA on activity of efflux pump respectively.

3. Testing Methods

3.1. Detection the Effect of Salicylic Acid on Antibiotic Sensitivity:

Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method [11] was applied to detect antibiotic sensitivity of *A. baumannii* isolates toward 21 type of antibiotics. MHA plates free from SA and MHA plates supplemented with 4mM of SA was inoculated with 100µl of bacterial suspension (adjusted to McFarland tube NO.0.5) by spreading method and left to dry for 10min.. The antibiotic discs were distributed on plates (6-7 disc/plate). The diameter of inhibition zone was measured before and after using SA and the results were detected as sensitive, intermediate, or resistant according to [12] guideline.

3.2. Detection the Effect of Salicylic Acid on Biofilm Formation:

Congo red agar method was followed up to detect the ability of isolate to form biofilms as mentioned previously [13]. Briefly, *A. baumannii* isolates were cultured on Congo Red Agar free from SA and Congo Red Agar supplemented with SA and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. The results are demonstrated as moderate biofilm formation when colonies appear as black to deep red in color while appearance of red colonies referred to weak biofilm formation. White colonies referred to inability of isolated to form biofilm. The results were compared before and after treatment with SA to evaluate the effect of SA on biofilm formation.

3.3. Detection the Effect of Salicylic acid on Activity of Efflux Pumps System:

Cart wheel method that described by [14] was carried out to detect the existence of efflux pumps in *A. baumannii* isolates. A fresh culture of *A. baumannii* on Brain heart infusion broth was centrifuge at 6000rpm for 10 min., then the pellet was re suspended with normal saline where the turbidity of suspension was adjusted to McFarland tube NO.0.5 (1.5 x 10⁵ cfu/ml). Five microliter of bacterial suspension was streak on TSA plates supplemented with different concentration of Ethidium Bromide as well as TSA plates supplemented with 4mM of SA and different concentration of Ethidium Bromide, and incubated at 37°C for 24hrs. At the end of incubation period the plates were allowed to dry at room temperature before being inspected under ultraviolet light. The capacity and ability of each isolates to extrude ethidium bromide to the outside was determined using a UV transilluminator. The

fluorescence at higher ethidium bromide concentrations had a more active efflux system than isolates with fluorescence at lower concentrations. The results were compared before and after treatment with SA to evaluate the effect of SA on activity of efflux pumps system.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Effect of Salicylic Acid on Antibiotics Resistance

Before using SA antibiotics susceptibility test showed that most clinical isolates of *A. baumannii* have highly variable resistance to antibiotics. *A. baumannii* resistance to antibiotics was determined depending on CLSI (2024) as shown in Figure 1 where high percent (100%) of resistance was reported to ampicillin, cefepime, ceftazidime, ceftriaxone, cefotaxime, cefoxitin, aztreonam followed by 94.28% to each amoxiclav, meropenem and 91.42% to chloramphenicol. The percentage of resistance to other studied antibiotics was range between 88.57% -51.48% while a low percentage of resistance was detected to colistin (34.28%). After Using of SA the results showed decrease in antibiotic resistance to most studied antibiotic as mention in figure 1.

A. baumannii is one of the most common and important nosocomial pathogens isolated from the patients admitted to different wards of hospitals and it has become an important cause of death in hospitalized patients, especially in the patients admitted to the ICU wards [15]. The current research revealed a high prevalence of antibiotic resistance *A. baumannii* especially to β -lactam and carbapenem. Many reports showed that drug-resistant strains of *A. baumannii* have emerged and developed extensively as a result of the growing prevalence of the use of β -lactam antibiotics [16]. *A. baumannii* isolates acquire resistance in various ways, for example, enzymatic degradation of antibiotics by cleavage of the drug via enzymes known as oxacillinases, target site modification, altered membrane permeability by modifications to outer membrane porins which lead to increase resistance to carbapenems, multidrug efflux pumps, and biofilm formation [17,18,10].

The results showed that using of SA cause decrease in antibiotics resistance to most studied antibiotic. Exposure of *A. baumannii* to SA has led to several observations. Decreasing of resistance to carbapenems may associated with diminishing of Oxacillinase-mediated carbapenem resistance during SA exposure and absence of outer membrane porin, CarO, so that carbapenems cannot interact with the membrane and degrade the cell wall [19, 20]. Also, losing of CarO lead to decrease resistance to imipenem [20].

Figure 1: The percentage of antibiotic resistance of *Acinetobacter baumannii* before and after using Salicylic acid

4.2. Effect of Salicylic Acid on Biofilm Formation

The results of biofilm formation test (Figure 2) showed that 6 (17.14%) isolates were noticed as strong biofilm producer where occurrence of black colonies indicated biofilm while 1 (2.80%) isolate showed weak biofilm producing and 28(80%) isolates denoted as non-biofilm forming due to appearance of red colonies.

Figure 2: The percentage of biofilm formation of *Acinetobacter baumannii*

The effect of SA on biofilm formation have been studied and the results showed only 1 isolate changed from weak to strong biofilm production, while the other isolates changed from strong biofilm producer to weak as mention in figure 3.

Bacteria possess many virulence factors such as biofilm formation, effector molecule excretion, exotoxins, motility, stress survival, host immune modulation, nutritional/metabolic factors, and antibiotic evasion systems that in some way inhibit normal host functions and thus provide an advantage for the pathogen [9]. Inhibition of these factors directly or prevents their production, lead to a higher chance of the human immune system for clearing a bacterial infection. The results showed that using of SA made change in biofilm formation and cause decrease in the ability of isolates to form biofilm this may due to the effectiveness of SA on bacterial membrane and distribution of CarO. Previous study revealed that *A. baumannii* and *P. aeruginosa* are aggressive biofilm formers, and in the presence of SAs a reduction in biofilm formation has been noticed [21,22]. As mention previously (Sykes et al.,2024) a variety of proteins implicated in biofilm formation, including CarO, OmpA, OprDlike, DcaP-like, PstS, LysM, and Omp33, so that , presence of SA lead to its interaction with the membrane and its associated proteins, possibly results in disrupting biofilm formation.

Figure 3: The Effect of Salicylic acid on biofilm formation of *Acinetobacter baumannii*. A: showed changed in biofilm formation from weak to strong, B: showed changed in biofilm formation from strong to weak.

4.3. Effect of Salicylic Acid on Activity of Efflux pumps

As seen in figure 4, all *A. baumannii* isolates that cultured on tryptic soy agar medium supplemented with different concentration of ethidium bromide have the ability to producing efflux pumps where a high activity of efflux pump to extrude ethidium bromide occur at high concentration (2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) which detected with high fluorescence under UV light.

The results of evaluation the effect of SA on activity of efflux pump showed decrease in activity of efflux pump in exclude of ethidium bromide outside bacterial cells. When compare the results before and after adding of SA, the results showed that instead of the presence of SA the efflux pump still active in exclude ethidium bromide but its activity was decrease which characterized by low fluorescence at a high concentration of ethidium bromide (Figure 5).

A. baumannii is an important and opportunistic pathogen that plays a major role in the pathogenicity of humans. Their ability to survive in natural niches and in the hospital environment could be associated with the efflux pump mechanisms. The main functions of efflux pump include evasion of naturally produced molecules and removal of metabolic products and toxins [23]. Also, it could be complicated in an early stage of infection, such as adhesion to host cells and colonization, remove generally used antibiotics from the cell in the therapy of infections caused by these bacteria [24]. The results showed that the presence of SA lead to decrease in activity of efflux pump where exposure to salicylic acid on surfaces could permit the inappropriate expression of the efflux pump [25].

Figure 4: The activity of efflux pump system to exclude different concentration (0.25, 0.5, 1, and 2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) of ethidium bromide (EtBr) outside of *Acinetobacter baumannii* cells detected by fluorescence under UV light.

Figure 5: The effect of 4mM of salicylic acid on the activity of efflux pump to exclude different concentration of ethidium bromide (EtBr) outside *Acinetobacter baumannii* cells.

The results showed that exposure to SA results in an increasing of susceptibility to some β lactam such as imipenem and aminoglycoside as well as biofilm formation and activity of efflux pump this may due to the effect of SA on the structure of porin in the cell membrane and the regulation of efflux pump operon. [26] noted that downregulation of the RND efflux pump *adeAB* and decreased expression of *adeRS* (regulatory component) resulted in an increase in susceptibility to imipenem, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and ceftriaxone which lead to reduce the efficiency of the efflux pump.

4. Conclusion

SA play role in decreasing antibiotic resistance and virulence factors of *A. baumannii* suggestion possibility to use it in combination with antibiotics as drug of choice for treated of infection caused by *A. baumannii*.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interests.

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